

Personal advertising on TikTok: how aware is generation Z regarding their data that is being collected by TikTok for personal advertising?

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ABSTRACT

The use of TikTok has grown exponentially in the last years across the world. Despite this popularity, countries concluding India have banned or restricted TikTok due to data security threats. Therefore, it is relevant to examine how the usage affects users' privacy and in particular the awareness of generation Z regarding data privacy.

This research aims to examine how secure the use of TikTok is in relation to safeguarding users' privacy. And specifically, the awareness of generation Z regarding. Due to the recent growth and the potential threads, this research is considered novel and socially relevant for the majority. The research question according to this research is:

“To what extent are the users of TikTok from generation Z aware of the potential risks of the data collection for personal advertising?”

The research contains desk research on the main topics of the research question. The results of it will be the input for the hypotheses and the survey. The participants in this research were tested on their awareness of the potential privacy risks associated with data collection for personal advertisements. These potential privacy risks arise due to inadequate data collection and usage of personal information. The test subjects show that they are less aware than they think they are. This is caused by contradictory results in the research.

Keywords: social media marketing, TikTok, digital privacy, data collection and personal advertising

Keywords

Guides, instructions, length, conference publications.

INTRODUCTION

There is a statement about the digital world, “if you are not paying for a product, then you are the product.”

The implication is that multiple social media services used daily (Facebook, TikTok, Google, Twitter etc.) earn money by supplying personal data to advertisers. Personal data of end users carry immense value for companies, platforms, and criminals for a variety of varied reasons. At its core, data is a resource. One of the platforms that collects data from users and is used to a considerable extent is TikTok.

The use of TikTok has grown exponentially in the last years across the world. In 2020 there were 465.7 million users worldwide on the platform. This amount increased to 655.9 million users in 2022. Online advertisers expect that the worldwide usage of TikTok will increase to 955.3 million. Despite this popularity, countries like India have banned or restricted TikTok due to data security threats.

The aim of this research is to examine how the awareness of generation Z regarding their data that is being collected for personalized advertising. There are a couple of studies available regarding TikTok combined with privacy. However, none of these articles specifically addresses data collection regarding personal advertisement. The main difference between data collection with the purpose for personal advertising has to do with the objectives. Data collection in general is practiced by platforms and websites to enhance user experience. As for personal advertising, the collected data will be utilized for offering products or services. As mentioned before, TikTok has grown exponentially, and it is forecasted that this growth will continue in the coming years. Along with the fact that the use of TikTok has caused a stir in more countries in relation to data security threats, this research is considered novel and socially relevant.

Answering the research question clarifies the coherence between the potential risks and the awareness of generation Z. The knowledge provided

by answering the main question can help *generation Z be more aware of the potential risks of the data collection for personal advertising.*

The research contains a brief desk research on the topics: the privacy policy of TikTok, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and personal advertisement. The aim of the desk research is to get an overview of the elements of the research question. The overview will be input for the disquisition of the assumptions which are going to be used in the survey to validate or reject the assumptions.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

As TikTok is growing exponentially in users worldwide. This creates chances for marketers to present personal advertisements to a rapidly growing audience. To be able to create personal advertisements data is collected on the user base of TikTok. This data is crucial for marketers to perform personal advertisements to the consumers of the application TikTok (TikTok, 2021). TikTok is popular among the Gen Z generation (41 % of their users), this raises the question of how aware are the users in the gen Z population of data collection on confidential information with a rapidly growing application like TikTok?

Multiple pieces of research have been conducted on the relationship between age and privacy awareness. However, the existing literature is contradicting itself. The first paper states that the privacy awareness score across all age groups is similar (Hazari & Brown, 2013). This is the awareness that does not relate to data collection specifically for personal advertisement as mentioned before. The second paper states that younger people are more aware of what data is collected than people in an older age group (Halperin & Dror, 2016). A third paper states as follows about persons under 18: “While they voluntarily enter this information into social-networking sites because of the social activities and enjoyment of the networking experience, they do not fully realize the issues associated with disclosing private information (Deborah & Christiansen, 2010).” The contradiction between the literature shows a knowledge gap in age being a potential factor in the responsible use of social media platforms in general.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The increasing usage of social media and TikTok, arisen opportunities for data collection and personal advertising. This trend comes not only with positive developments, but also potential threats to users’ privacy. As mentioned in the previous

sections of this paper, are the threats verily a reason for concern and creating awareness among youthly users. With the limited research available on TikTok as well as on privacy regarding data collection, the knowledge gap that we seek to address will be found in the following research question: *To what extent are the users of TikTok from generation Z aware of the potential risks of the data collection for personal advertising?*

RQ1: What are the potential risks associated with data collection for personal advertising?

RQ2: To what extent is generation Z aware of the data that is collected by TikTok for personal advertising?

These sub-questions collectively answer the main question. The sub-questions will be answered due to two different approaches namely, a literature study to distinguish the potential risks. And beyond answering the first question, the output of RQ1 will be the input for the surveys on the target audience (TikTok users within generation Z) to collect primary data. Answering and merging these separate sub-questions, covers the overall scope of the research question.

THEORY

Digital privacy

Privacy is defined in by Westin (1967) as: “the claim of individuals, groups or institutions to determine for themselves when, how, and to what extent information about them is communicated to others”

Apart from Westin's basic definition, there is not really another general definition to be given of the concept of privacy. Indeed, the definition depends very much on the context in which it is found. However, it can be concluded that privacy today is related to the protection of personal data, where confidentiality is seen as preventing disclosure of information to certain individuals or groups (Papanikolaou, Vlachos, Chatzimisios, & Illioudis, 2013).

Regarding digital/online privacy, there are three main rights that users should be able to obtain that can protect privacy (Opsahl, 2010):

- The right to decision-making where the user is informed: Users should be able to decide who has access to their personal data. Decision-making information also includes how the data is used.

- The right to control Users should retain control over how their data is used (Opsahl, 2010).

- The right to leave users should also have the right to be able to stop using a digital platform. They should therefore be able to have their data erased or exported so that their data is owned by themselves.

Besides the basic definition and main right, this section will also focus on threats in relation to digital privacy, within social networks. The input for this section is a paper form (Erlandsson, Boldt, & Johnson, 2012). This article sums six threats:

- The first threat is information leakage by the network of the platform itself. This means that personal information such as user profile content, photos and messages can be mined or sold by the network of platforms.

- The second threats have to do with the risk that a trusted 'friend' shares information

- A Trojan application is an installed application which is presented as desired functionality, but in fact mines valuable information

- Public information harvesting means that third parties collect personal data published in open groups within the network or platforms.

- A Social bot is an automated software program that imitates human behavior on social media. By infiltrating friend relationships these bots can collect personal information.

- The last threat is the Friend-in-the-Middle Trojan Application. This threat is an indirect consequence of the earlier described Trojan application. If a friend is exposed to such an application, the initial user's data can be collected through the relationship.

Social media behavior of generation z

Another element of the theory is the behavior form generation Z regarding social media usage. Generation Z was born between 1997 and 2011. A characteristic from generation Z is that they are the first generation which have technology in terms of internet readily available. Besides that, this generation grew up being exposed to an unprecedented amount of technology (Prakash Yadav & Rai, 2017). Social media is described by Prakash Yadav & Rai (2017) as: "any electronic service through which Internet users are able to

create and share a variety of contents over the Internet" Unlike earlier generations, social media is a large part of social interaction within generation Z. The main rationale behind the use of social media by gen z is the need to be involved and informed with other people (Prakash Yadav & Rai, 2017). In relation to the other generations, gen z is a vigorous contributor, high consumer of online content, with a strong gravitational bond for online communication (Prakash Yadav & Rai, 2017).

GDPR

The general data protection regulation (GDPR from now on) is a set of laws in the European Union (EU from now on) to ensure the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data. This regulation was implemented in 2016 and is the protector of article 12 of the United Nations' universal declaration of human rights where no one will be subject to arbitrary interference with their privacy (United Nations, n.d.).

This law applies to all organizations that operate in the EU or European Economic area (Wolford, 2019). According to art. 12 of the GDPR, a controller is obliged to provide transparency regarding the information that is collected from the data subject (Intersoft consulting, n.d-b). The controllers are allowed to collect personal data like name, e-mail address and location. But they are not allowed to collect any type of personal data that, by their nature, form a potential threat to their fundamental rights or freedom. This includes data such as race, ethnic origin, biometric data, and political preference (Intersoft consulting, n.d-c). Besides that, the data subject has the right to get insight into all data that the controller has collected from them and if requested, to be deleted (Intersoft consulting, n.d.-a).

Privacy policy of TikTok

The privacy policy that TikTok made, applies to all personal information that they, as the data controller, collect and process through all TikTok-related applications, platforms, and websites (TikTok, 2021). The information that TikTok collects is divided into three categories, namely: self-provided information, automatically collected information and information from other sources. The provided information contains data such as profile information, personal contacts, transaction and purchase history and direct messages (TikTok, 2021).

Automatically collected information concerns data like location and specifically SIM card and IP

address. Also, technical information is collected like device model, operating system, keystrokes, and login information through multiple different devices (TikTok, 2021). Lastly information from other sources is data that is supplied by advertisers, data partners and third-party platforms (TikTok, 2021). These parties share information with TikTok regarding mobile identifiers for advertising purposes like actions taken on an app or website. The TikTok pixel is a line of code that collects those actions and supplies it to advertisers to see which pages of the app or website have been visited (TikTok, 2021). The purpose of this collection usually is to determine how advertisements can be optimized to reach certain goals like conversation rate or level of engagement (TikTok, 2021).

Social media marketing

Social media marketing can be defined as offering or promoting products or services through social media platforms to reach out to a specific target audience. This allows companies to improve the customer relationships or acquire new customers and to advance their value proposition in a fitting manner. Past studies concluded that social media marketing leads to improved customer trust, enhanced customer intimacy, engagement, and awareness. (Han & Kim, 2020).

Khan (2022) did a relevant study where the degree of purchase intention and perspective on brands were impacted by social media marketing activities. The two moderating subgroups were millennials and non-millennials where results were expressed in customer engagement (high and low). The observations in the study indicate that social media marketing activities are more likely to influence the perception of millennials compared to non-millennials. This study among others concludes that (Zollo, Filieri, Rialti, & Yoon, 2020) social media marketing plays a key role in influencing the perception of companies by the end users of social media platforms.

Conceptual model

In figure 1, the conceptual model regarding this research paper is illustrated. The model consists of three elements of the research question. The aim of this research is to investigate the awareness of generation Z regarding privacy risks. If this awareness is measured, it can contribute to improving responsible TikTok usage by generation Z. When the users are aware of the potential risks, they can use TikTok in a better informed way. Furthermore, the model contains the element, risk

due to data collection for personal advertisement. The assumption is that TikTok usage by gen Z will lead to data collection for personal advertising, and this can lead to potential privacy risks. This assumption will be confirmed or disproved by connecting the results of the different elements of the theory exploration. The theory section reveals the elements of the main question in a generic, informative way. Further on in the results, additional theory answers RQ1 in a more specific, subjective way.

Although this assumption contains a large part of the conceptual model, it is not the focus of the field research. The field research will focus on examining Generation Z's current level of awareness about the data collected from them and what the potential associated risks are. The second assumption stems from the problem statement. Here it is indicated that 41% of TikTok users are from generation Z. The literature review also revealed that this target group is a large consumer of social media. Often, social interaction of gen z is through social media. In addition, an assumption was made in the problem statement that generation Z does not always use social media responsibly due to its youthful age. Hence, the focus of the field research will be examining the extent to which generation Z is aware of the risks associated with TikTok usage. Input to perform the field research will be the results of the theory study.

Figure 1. Conceptual model.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to find out to what extent generation Z is aware of the risks regarding data collection for personalized advertisements on TikTok. To achieve this, we chose to first conduct a theoretical exploration of the main elements of the research question. These results can be observed in the 'theory' section. Besides ensuring that this literature review dissects and presents knowledge on the topics, it also serves as a framework to initiate the field research. Indeed, the output of the theory will start to serve as the foundation for the questions in the survey that will be conducted. For the theory study, scholarly sources were used. In addition to scientific sources, publications of an intergovernmental organization were used. Moreover, publicly available information about TikTok was also used, referring to the privacy policy. The non-scientific sources have only been used to explore and clarify objective topics such as the GDPR and TikTok's privacy policy. The reason

a survey was chosen as the field research method is since there is little time to collect and analyze the required data. In addition, the target group being approached (Generation Z) is easier to reach with a survey than interviews. This makes it a low threshold for the target group to participate in the field research. Another motive for choosing a survey is scope. By using google docs software, the survey can be formed, distributed and the data can be analyzed more easily. Distributing a link for participation is less time-consuming than scheduling multiple interviews. The choice for generation Z lies in the fact that they make up a substantial proportion of people using TikTok (41%). In addition, the young people in this target group may not always be careful when using social media. The theory has also shown that a large part of this target group's social interaction takes place on social media. The questions that will be asked of this target group include Multiple choice questions, questions where the respondents can answer within a given scale (Likert scale). Furthermore, there will be control questions to check if the answers that are given by the respondents are useful. In case the four surveys are not useful, the same number of surveys will be distributed again to achieve the twenty respondents. It is chosen to not include open-ended questions. The reason for this choice is to maintain a structured data input for the analyses.

To ensure that the survey questions were interpreted correctly it was decided to present the survey to five people from the target group beforehand. They can answer the questions and provide feedback afterward. This safeguards the quality of the output of the survey.

To calculate the sample size, the population size is required. It can be concluded, based on the database of the Central bureau of statistics (CBS Statlined, n.d.), that generation Z (between the ages of 12 and 27) comprises 3,365,551 people in the Netherlands in 2017. In addition, a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error were chosen. The corresponding Z value at the chosen confidence interval is 1.96. Based on these data and criteria, the sample should be taken from 385 individuals from the population to provide a representative conclusion on generation Z. In figure 2 the formula for calculating the sample size is illustrated. However, within the timeframe of this study, it is unfortunately not possible to achieve 385 respondents and analyze the corresponding data in time. For that reason, it was chosen by 20 respondents. It is clear to the researchers that this is at the expense of the reliability and validity of the study. This is discussed in more detail in the limitations section.

The 5-point Likert scale data will be exported to SPSS and analyzed using SPSS. The interpretation of the output will be done based on the mean and standard deviation of the output. Besides the mean and standard deviation regarding the questionnaire, the Cronbach alpha of these questions will also be taken into consideration. This to ensure internal consistency of the question that measures the same variable. To analyze the output of the survey, the results were converted into a common, standard numerical format. Besides the statistical analysis, the questions are analyzed by the distribution of the answers (Yes or No questions for example).

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2} \div \left(1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N} \right) \right)$$

Figure 2. Formula Sample size population survey

RESULTS

Repeating RQ1: How do potential risks because of data collection for personal advertising affect digital privacy?

Risks in the context of data collection for personal advertising refers to the unwanted consequences because of social media usage (Ayarubi & Treku, 2020). Examples of those risks (Hedayati, 2012) include identity theft because of data breaches, device hacking, reputation damage, fraud, and cyber stalking.

Data collection for personal advertising through social media platforms is also referred to as data mining. Data mining is the process of gathering and acquiring information (Tan, Steinbach, & Kumar, 2006) through raw data to receive useful information for, among others, decision-making. Furthermore, social media platforms use data mining for personal advertising by utilizing pattern recognition, algorithms, database systems and data warehousing (Han, Kamber, & Pei, 2011).

The lack of awareness relates to these unintended consequences and the complex privacy statements on social media platforms enable those risks. Jafar and Abdullat (2011) found that most privacy policies were only readable to users who have attended at least two years of tertiary education. Most social media users in the United States are not college-educated (Clement, 2019) and that results in users being less likely to be aware of

potential risks mentioned before or even to use social media irresponsibly.

Among other threats are economic loss and intellectual property theft. Hackers and cyber criminals could use ransomware (O’Kane, Sezer, Carlin, 2018) which is a type of malware to render digital tools inaccessible or unusable to extort the victims and extract money from them.

Repeating RQ2: *To what extent is generation Z aware of the data that is collected by TikTok for personal advertising?* As mentioned in the methodology a survey was used to find input for the research question. In total there were twenty-five respondents, but after analyzing the control questions about the target group, only twenty-one usable responses remained to subtract information from. Four respondents answered that they were not part of generation Z, and these respondents did not use TikTok at all. In the rest of this section, the analysis of the survey will be presented in the same sequence as that the questions were asked.

First, the respondents were asked if they were aware of the data collection in TikTok. Sixty-two percent of the respondents answered to be aware or very aware of the data collection (N = 21) (see appendix 1).

Furthermore, there were questions asked about the abilities that TikTok users have about their data and personalized advertisement. The question about the overview of the collected data is: Did you know that the data that is collected from you can be requested through TikTok? 57,1% of the respondents answered this question with No. The question about personalized advertisements is: Are you aware that instead of personal advertisements, you can also receive general advertisements by turning off data collection? 61,9% of the respondents answered that they are not aware of the possibility to switch personalized advertisements off.

After this introduction, the respondents were asked eight more in-depth questions if the respondents were aware of the following list of data that is collected:

- Profile information.
- Contact information.
- Transaction and purchase history.
- Location information.
- SIM card information.
- Device model information.
- Keyboard patterns.
- IP address information.

The Cronbach alpha of these eight has been checked to validate the internal consistency of the

questions (see appendix 2). The result of the analysis illustrates that the threshold (0.7) for sufficient internal consistency is nearly reached (0.667).

The respondents could answer on a 5-point Likert scale with 1 = Very unaware, 2 = Unaware, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Aware, 5 = Very aware. In appendix 3 the mean and standard deviation is shown per question. As seen in appendix 3 the respondents are the most aware of the profile information collected (M = 3,24; SD = 0,944) and the least on TikTok collection the keyboard patterns (M = 2,52; SD = 1,250). The answers given on the questions about awareness about the type of information that is collected is varying around one, the mean of standard deviation is 0,989. The mean of all eight questions is 2,8675.

One of the last questions of the survey concerned the extent to which respondents felt they were informed well enough about the data being collected from it (see appendix 4). The question was asked after respondents were exposed to the various information that TikTok collects from them for getting personalized ads. Sixty-five percent of those surveyed indicated that they disagreed or totally disagreed. Only 25% said they were informed by TikTok.

DISCUSSION

Based on the respondents 57.1% answered to be aware of the data being collected by TikTok and 4.9% answered to be very aware of the data collected (see figure 3). However, in the follow-up questions the respondents were asked if they were aware of specific data being collected by TikTok. The results in table 3 show that 75% of the questions score a mean lower than 3. This shows that the respondents lean more toward being unaware than toward being aware (2= Unaware, 3 = neutral, 4 = Aware).

Furthermore, in appendix 4 it is shown that 55% of the respondents disagree that TikTok has given good enough notice about the data they collect. This shows a mismatch between the respondents thinking they are aware of the data being collected but if the facts are shown they disagree with the notice of TikTok.

Furthermore, research has been done on the influence of specific questions on Cronbach’s alpha to improve the overall Cronbach’s alpha. As seen in appendix 56, a Cronbach alpha of 0.671 can be reached by deleting the question about the awareness of the collection of IP addresses.

The Cronbach alpha of the questions is 0.667 (nearly the threshold of 0.7. This means every question that should measure the awareness of generation z about the data that TikTok collects

from them, measures the same thing. One of the reasons for not achieving the desired Cronbach alpha of 0.7 is stated in the limitations.

CONCLUSION

The initial research focussed on the risks of data collection for personal advertising by the use of social media. However, when starting the research it was concluded that the research question was not specific enough because a comparison between every social media needed to be made. Thus the research questions were narrowed down to TikTok only and the gen z generation to make the research questions specific.

The research paper answers the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the potential risks associated with data collection for personal advertising?

The purpose of this research question was to discover the risks that come along with the usage of services that collect personal data for personal advertising. Numerous risks come forth when this data is collected. To mention few, identity theft because of data breaches, device hacking, reputation damage, fraud, and cyberstalking. Another topic that is not necessarily intrinsically a risk, but is the source of the other potential risks to occur is the fact that according to research, a large portion of the users experiences hardship in reading the privacy policies. This leads to users that are ignorant about the privacy policy and could cause irresponsible usage of the platforms.

RQ2: To what extent is generation Z aware of the data that is collected by TikTok for personal advertising?

The research shows that gen z believes to be completely aware of the data collected by TikTok for personal advertising. However, the survey used in the research concludes that gen z is in general only aware for 25% of the data that is collected by TikTok and presented in the survey. This reinforces the statement about the digital world, "if you are not paying for a product, then you are the product." and deems it to be true.

With the outcome of these research questions the main research question can be answered:

"To what extent are the users of TikTok from generation Z aware of the potential risks of the data collection for personal advertising?"

The answer to the main question is two-part. The first part relates to the potential risks regarding data collection for personal advertising. The second part relates to awareness about the data collected from it

by TikTok. These two separate parts can be linked together through the fact that the collection and distribution of personal information for data collection is accompanied by some risks described in the first sub-question (RQ1). Data breaches are the most obvious associated risks regarding data collection for personal advertising. Furthermore, fraud and reputation damage are reasonable risks associated with data collection for personal advertising. To illustrate this link; Indeed, inappropriate collection and use of collected data by TikTok may cause the data collected by TikTok to fall into the wrong hands of individuals and organizations that have other purposes with your data as opposed to personal advertising. They may, against these wrong interests, use the user's data in rogue practices causing data breaches. These breaches, in turn, can lead to reputational damage as users' data pops up in places it shouldn't be.

It can be concluded that generation Z is not fully aware of the data collected from them on TikTok regarding personalized advertisements. Not fully aware can be quantified by the fact that of the eight data points that were presented to the respondents, they only indicated at two that they are aware that the data is being collected from them, namely profile information and transaction history. This combined with the fact that 62% indicated that they were minimally aware it can be concluded that the perception of generation Z regarding the awareness of the potential risk of the data collection for personal advertising is not in line with the results of the research.

Limitations

This research is subject to limitations that prevent the study from being completely reliable and valid. First of all, the sample size related to the formula from the method section was not used. This is because it is almost impossible to find 385 respondents who fall within the target group within the relatively short time frame. It was decided to go for a feasible number of respondents, namely 20. While releasing this, the researchers are aware that this is at the expense of the representativeness of the target group (TikTok users of generation Z).

In addition, the aim was to achieve a reasonable Cronbach alpha of at least .7. Due to the relatively low number of questions addressing the awareness of generation Z regarding the data collected from it (8 questions), a Cronbach alpha of 0.667 was achieved. However, it is assumed that partly due to the low sample size, internal consistency of the questions was achieved. It was also not possible for the survey to draw a complete profile of Generation Z. This is because the range of ages within this generation varies widely (born

between 1997 and 2011). Most respondents fell into the category born between 1997 and 2000. There is awareness that this does not give a pure picture of generation Z. In addition, the range of generation Z is fairly abstract. For instance, different sources indicate different birth years. For this study, the following ranks were used; born between 1997 and 2011. There is also determination to use surveys instead of interviews. This is because of ease in distribution, participation and analysis. However, interviews could give a better picture of respondents' perceptions. A measurable framework to determine when a user is aware or not is missing. Finally, the questions in the survey could give a more complete answer to the main question if the risks associated with social media usage were included. The reason that most of the above limitations have occurred has to do with the relatively short time in which this study should be delivered. If more time and financial resources were available, this study would have been a lot more reliable and valid.

Further research

As indicated in the limitation, the study is not completely reliable and valid. This is because of the relatively short time. This is one reason why a smaller sample size was chosen for the interview as opposed to the formulaic calculation for this group. It was also chosen in this study to take some data collected by TikTok (source privacy statement) and test whether respondents are aware that this data is collected. For further research, it is therefore advisable to start investigating what data is actually collected from other social media platforms. One way for this could be by making a request to the relevant medium for a representative group for the data collected. Another method of field research, e.g. an interview, is also recommended in follow-up research. This may allow, for example, further questions to be asked on certain answers. It is also advisable to start doing similar research for other social media platforms with a sample size that can better represent the validity and reliability of Generation Z. Follow-up research on generation Z's digital privacy regarding the data collected from them on social media platforms. Furthermore, it is highly recommended to use a framework to plot awareness. This research used a likert scale and the corresponding statistical methods to analyze the awareness of the respondents. However, a concrete and reasoned framework would better justify the results. The potential conducted research can be shared among institutions where generation z is represented. This can contribute to a more informed and responsible usage of TikTok.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix 1

Are you aware of what data is collected by TikTok?

21 responses

Figure 1. Awareness of Gen Z about data collected by TikTok

Appendix 2

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,667	,660	8

Appendix 3

Table 2. Item Statistics

Item Statistics								
	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects profile information to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects contacts information to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects transaction and purchase history to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects location information to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects SIM card information to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects device model to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects keyboard patterns to create personalized ads for you?	To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects IP-address information to create personalized ads for you?
Mean	3,24	2,76	3,19	2,81	2,71	2,90	2,52	2,81
Std. Deviation	,944	,995	1,078	,928	,845	,944	1,250	,928
N	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21

Appendix 4

Figure 2. Gen Z's opinion on TikTok's privacy notice

Appendix 5

Table 3. Item-Total Statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects profile information to create personalized ads for you?	19,71	14,914	,445	,672	,616
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects contacts information to create personalized ads for you?	20,19	15,362	,345	,517	,639
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects transaction and purchase history to create personalized ads for you?	19,76	14,790	,373	,433	,633
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects location information to create personalized ads for you?	20,14	15,129	,423	,548	,621
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects SIM card information to create personalized ads for you?	20,24	16,390	,284	,592	,653
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects device model to create personalized ads for you?	20,05	16,248	,251	,377	,661
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects keyboard patterns to create personalized ads for you?	20,43	12,757	,530	,580	,584
To what extent are you aware that TikTok collects IP-address information to create personalized ads for you?	20,14	16,629	,206	,354	,671